

These studies produced very strong evidence in favour of the 1-amidino-O-alkylurea structures for these compounds⁶.

This paper presents the results of infra-red spectral studies and the data fully support the structure proposed by the Japanese and substantiated by the Americans by way of independent syntheses.

With a view to obtaining confirmation we considered it worthwhile to compare the infra-red spectra of some members obtained by the template syntheses with those of the amidinourea. The major structural difference between the alternative structures of 1-amidino-3-alkylurea and 1-amidino-O-alkylurea will be that the first group ligands will have a carbonyl group which will be missing from the second family of ligands. The latter, on the other hand, will show an O-alkyl group which will be absent in the 1-amidino-3-alkylureas and amidinoureas. We studied amidinourea as representative of the first and 1-amidino-O-methylurea and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea as representative of the second class. Infra-red spectral bands for these three ligands and their probable assignments are given in Table I. It may be noted that the band at 1200 cm^{-1} appears both in 1-amidino-O-methylurea and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea but is completely absent in amidinourea. It is this band which involves C-O-R asymmetric stretching vibration. Again bands 1680 cm^{-1} and 1740 cm^{-1} which are associated with amide I and C=O respectively are strikingly missing from the spectra of 1-amidino-O-methylurea and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea. In the event of the ligand having 1-amidino-3-alkylurea configuration, there could be expected strong absorption bands around 2800 cm^{-1} arising out of C-H vibrations associated with -NH-R^8 . But such bands are absent from the spectra of 1-amidino-O-methylurea as also of 1-amidino-O-ethylurea. Thus these qualitative band assignments immediately rule out the presence of C=O band in the template reaction products as believed to be present originally.

In nickel (I) bis 1-amidino-O-methylurea chloride which we ran as a further check, a very strong sharp peak appears around 1210 cm^{-1} corroborating the presence of C-O-R group in the complex. The absence of strong bands in the 1700 cm^{-1} region is a further check against any possible carbonyl structure involved in the complex.

Further to these infrared studies we have one analytical evidence to support the O-alkylurea structure. We have determined by a careful Zeisel technique the amount of the methoxyl group present in 1-amidino-O-methylurea, and the result comes quite close to that expected for the proposed structure of 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate.*

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*Dr. D. Sen of Jadavpur University also informs us of a similar Zeisel estimation of 1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate with comparable results.

TABLE I

*Infra-red group frequencies of amidinourea, 1-amidino-O-methylurea and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea sulphates and their band assignments.**

Amidinourea sulphate**	1-amidino-O-methylurea sulphate	1-amidino-O-ethylurea sulphate	Nature of vibration
Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	Frequency, cm ⁻¹	
1125 v.s.	1120 v.s.	1120 v.s.	Sulphate ¹⁰
	1200 v.s.	1200 v.s.	C-O-R stretching vibration ¹⁷
1350 v.s.	1400 v.s.	1350 v.s.	C-N stretching vibration ¹⁸
	1400 v.s.	1400 v.s.	C-H symmetrical deformation vibration ¹³
1465 v.s.	1480 v.s.	1485 v.s.	-NH ₂ † symmetrical bend ¹⁴
1530 w	1520 s.	1540 v.s.	N-H deformation vibration ¹⁵
1580 s.	1550 v.s.	1580 v.s.	
1625 w.***	1600 v.s.		
1680 v.s.	1645 v.s.	1645 v.s.	C=NH vibration ¹⁶
1740 v.s.			Amide I band ¹⁷
3180 s.	3190 v.s.	3200 v.s.	C=O absorption band ¹⁶
3320 s.	3280 sh.	330 sh.	N-H and -NH ₂ stretching vibrations ¹⁵⁻¹⁶
3350 s.	3310 v.s.	3350 v.s.	

EXPERIMENTAL

1-amidino-O-methylurea (AMUH) sulphate and 1-amidino-O-ethylurea sulphate were prepared by the reaction between dicyandiamide and the respective alcohols in the presence of copper (II) acetate¹. The crude materials were recrystallised three to four times from water and finally their spectra recorded in Beckman Infra-red Spectrophotometer by the KBr pellet technique. Amidinourea sulphate was also obtained by following standard procedure²¹ of heating dicyandiamide with dilute sulphuric acid. The crude product

*s=strong; v.s. very strong; sh=shoulder; w=weak.

**The infrared spectra of amidinourea compounds has already been described in relation to urea and guanidine¹⁶. Our studies confirm these previous results.

***This band may also be assigned to amide II band¹⁷.

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was recrystallised thrice from water and spectra recorded as above. The nickel(II) complex was prepared and purified by published method²² and run as KBr pellet technique.

Methoxyl group determination was made by standard Zeisel technique²². Found:: OCH₃, 16.5%. (AMUH), SO₄, 2H₂O requires OCH₃, 16.9%.

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INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
THE UNIVERSITY OF BURDWAN,
BURDWAN.

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